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Description of human emotions in Guy de Maupassant's works

Abstract

This article analyzes an extraordinarily productive writer Guy de Maupassant whose short stories dealt with such diverse themes as war, love, marital infidelity, religion, madness, cultural misunderstanding between the French and the English, and life in the French provinces, especially his native Normandy. His short stories varied greatly in length from only a few pages to more than forty pages. His stories are extremely well organized, and there is much psychological depth in his insights into the complex motivations for his characters' behavior. His work explores the full spectrum of French society. In this article we aimed to underline the descriptions of human emotions in his works. He describes characters from various professions and social classes with sensitivity and humor.

Key words: *humor, naturalism, romanticism, realistic literature, human emotions, theme of the works.*

Guy de Maupassant, (born Aug. 5, 1850, Château de Miromesnil, near Dieppe, France; died July 6, 1893, Paris), French writer of short stories. His law studies were interrupted by the Franco-Prussian War; his experience as a volunteer provided him with material for some of his best works. Later, as a civil-service employee, he became a protégé of Gustave Flaubert. He first gained attention with "Boule de Suif" (1880; "Ball of Fat"), probably his finest story. In the next 10 years he published some 300 short stories, six novels, and three travel books. Taken together, his stories present a broad, naturalistic picture of French life from 1870 to 1890. His subjects include war, the Norman peasantry, the bureaucracy, life on the banks of the Seine, the emotional problems of the different classes, and, ominously, hallucination. Maupassant was phenomenally promiscuous, and before he

was 25 years old his health was being eroded by syphilis. He attempted suicide in 1892 and was committed to an asylum, where he died at age 42. He is generally considered France's greatest master of the short story.

When the great French writer Guy de Maupassant stepped on the threshold of creativity, he was confronted with a literary legacy of three generations – Stendhal, Balzac, and Flaubert's critical realism; Gyugo, J. Sand and A. de Myusse romanticism and. There was naturalism, led by E. Zolya and the Gonkur brothers. For this reason, critics who later studied Mopassan's work said that all three school traditions could be seen in his works.¹⁶

Indeed, although the author himself claims to have followed Stendhal, Balzac, and Flaubert realism, when we read his novels and novels we see both the exaggerated expressions characteristic of the school of Romanticism and the depiction of human physiognomy and ancestral evolution in the writers of naturalism. Nevertheless, the literature of critical realism had a great influence on the formation and perfection of the writer's work. The years 1880-1890 were the heyday of Mopassan's work. During these years he published sixteen collections of short stories, six novels, three books of memoirs, and hundreds of literary-critical essays. The writer lived a humble life, despite his great fame. He wanted his works to always be popular. That is why the writer, in his works, sought to give a realistic coverage of the events of the people's life. The lives of those belonging to the "superior race" in bourgeois society were sharply satirized in Mopassan's works, and the activities of government agencies, where laziness and bureaucracy were rampant, were brutally exposed. The writer also openly expressed his hatred of bourgeois literature and the press in his works.¹⁷ In his other novels, written in 1882-1883, we see that Maupassant sought to escape the influence of naturalism. Critical realism plays a leading role in the plot of the author's short stories, which are included in the collections "Waldshnep's stories", "Mademoiselle Fifi", "Moonlit night". In these short stories, the author follows in the footsteps of Stendhal, Balzac and Flaubert and depicts the situation in real paintings. In this way he proves that the novella genre is not inferior to the novel genre in the realistic

¹⁶ The life and work of Guy de Mopassan are covered in detail in the following sources: Y.I.Danilin. Mopassan. Jizn and creativity. M; 1968. History of French literature. M; Izd-vo AN SSSR, 1959, tom III, pp.191-233.

¹⁷ Guy de Mopassan's Life, "My Dear." Tashkent, Gafur Gulam Publishing House of Literature and Art, 1987 Page 6

depiction of reality. As Zolya puts it, Maupassant "in his four- to five-page short stories expressed the content of the great works of the novelists."¹⁸

□*La Maison Tellier*" (1881; □The Tellier House□), a book of short stories on various subjects, is typical of Maupassant□s achievement as a whole, both in his choice of themes and in his determination to present men and women objectively in the manifold aspects of life. His concern was with 1□humble vérité□ words which he chose as the subtitle to his novel "*Une Vie*" (1883; A Woman□s Life). This book, which sympathetically treats its heroine□s journey from innocent girlhood through the disillusionment of an unfortunate marriage and ends with her subsequent widowhood, records what Maupassant had observed as a child, the little dramas and daily preoccupations of ordinary people. He presents his characters dispassionately, foregoing any personal moral judgment on them but always noting the word, the gesture, or even the reticence that betrays each one□s essential personality, all the while enhancing the effect by describing the physical and social background against which his characters move. Concision, vigour, and the most rigorous economy are the characteristics of his art.

Although Maupassant appeared outwardly a sturdy, healthy, athletic man, his letters are full of lamentations about his health, particularly eye trouble and migraine headaches. With the passing of the years he had become more and more somber. He had begun to travel for pleasure, but what had once been carefree and enjoyable holidays gradually changed, as a result of his mental state, into compulsive, symptomatic wanderings until he felt a constant need to be on the move.

Conclusion

Maupassant□s work is thoroughly realistic. His characters inhabit a world of material desires and sensual appetites in which lust, greed, and ambition are the driving forces, and any higher feelings are either absent or doomed to cruel disappointment. The tragic power of many of the stories derives from the fact that Maupassant presents his characters, poor people or rich bourgeois, as the victims of ironic necessity, crushed by a fate that they have dared to defy yet still struggling against it hopelessly.

¹⁸ Guy de Mopassan's "Life," "My Dear." Tashkent, Gafur Gulam Publishing House of Literature and Art, 1987 Page 8

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